

Diluted nitride type-II superlattices: overcoming the difficulties of bulk alloys in solar cells

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The lack of suitable semiconductor materials is nowadays hindering the realization of multi-junction solar cells with conversion efficiencies close to the theoretical limits. Here type-II GaAsSb/GaAsN superlattices (SL) are demonstrated as an adequate structure to form the lattice-matched 1.0-1.15 eV subcell that would allow the implementation of the optimum monolithic multi-junction solar cell design. The spatial separation of N and Sb leads to an improved composition homogeneity and a lower defect density than in the bulk GaAsSbN counterparts. The type-II band alignment in SLs provides long radiative lifetimes that facilitate carrier collection as compared to the type-I equivalents. Moreover, the radiative lifetime can be controllably tuned through the period thickness, something that is not achievable in type-I SLs. A reduced period thickness results in enhanced absorption due to increased wavefunction overlap, as well as in a change in the transport regime from diffusive to quasiballistic, providing improved carrier extraction efficiency. As a result, the short period SL single-junction solar cells show an enhanced power conversion efficiency of 134% over the equivalent bulk devices.

1. Introduction

Semiconductor multi-junction solar cells hold the records of power conversion efficiency for many years. Indeed, this is the only approach within the so-called third generation of solar cells that has effectively overcome the Shockley-Queisser efficiency limit. The solar cell efficiency tables^[1] show that multi-junction solar cells are close to reaching an efficiency of 50%: 46.0% under concentration and 39.2% under AM1.5 conditions. Nevertheless, this technology still performs well below its theoretical limit because of technological problems in implementing the optimum multi-junction designs with the ideal lattice constant-bandgap energy combination. The lack of suitable high-quality semiconductor materials with the right bandgap energies that can be grown lattice-matched on to each other results in the requirement of complex technologies, such as wafer bonding or inverted metamorphic structures, which reduce the throughput and increase the fabrication costs. For instance, the addition of a lattice-matched sub-cell tuned to the 1.0-1.15 eV spectral range to the standard (Al)InGaP/(In)GaAs/Ge solar cell structure provides such an optimum multi-layer design.^[2,3] Such configuration would easily leave behind the 50% efficiency according to theoretical calculations when operated under concentration.^[4,5] Therefore, materials lattice-matched to GaAs/Ge with a 1.0 eV or 1.15 eV bandgap are being extensively investigated.

Dilute nitride alloys arise at this point as a main candidate. These highly mismatched alloys, in which column V atoms in (In)GaAs(Sb) are partially replaced with N, experience an atypically strong bandgap reduction with the addition of small amounts of N, which allows tuning the bandgap easily to 1.15 and 1.0 eV.^[6] This effect is explained in the framework of the band anti-crossing (BAC) model as the result of a strong interaction between the localized N states and the conduction band of the matrix.^[6] Moreover, the alloys can be grown lattice-matched to GaAs/Ge and show a large absorption coefficient, due to the increased joint density of states arising from a

larger electron effective mass and thus a better matching to the hole band dispersion.^[7-9] Indeed, the only successful approach up to now towards the optimum multi-junction design was to use the GaInNAsSb dilute nitride alloy, which led to two consecutive world efficiency records set by Solar Junction CA.^[10] Such GaInP/GaAs/GaInNAsSb solar cells had an efficiency of 44.0% under concentration, below the theoretical limit, since epitaxial growth and material quality problems inherent to quaternary and quinary dilute nitride alloys seriously affect carrier dynamics.^[11] Despite the intense activity of many groups and some relevant advances,^[12-25] no improvements in conversion efficiency with three or four-junction cells have been certified since 2015.^[1]

We have recently proposed that the use of GaAsSb/GaAsN superlattices (SL) might solve these problems.^[26] These novel structures have the advantages of the highly mismatched dilute nitride alloys while at the same time avoid most of their inconveniences. The same effective bandgap can be achieved with half the N content than in the GaAsSbN bulk counterparts, which should result in an overall reduction of N-induced defects. The spatial separation of N and Sb allows an accurate composition control not achievable in GaAsSbN bulk and also results in improved crystal quality.^[26,27] Remarkably, Sb affects mainly the valence band of GaAs, while N affects only the conduction band, which allows an independent control of conduction and valence bands through the N and Sb contents, respectively.^[28] These structures are therefore very versatile in terms of band structure engineering, allowing an independent tuning of the electron and hole electronic coupling. Moreover, they show a type-II band alignment, with electrons confined in the GaAsN layer and holes in the GaAsSb, which should lead to long radiative carrier lifetimes and may have potential advantages for carrier collection.

In this work, we first use a combination of several state-of-the-art techniques to study the structural and optical properties of GaAsSb/GaAsN SLs grown by molecular beam epitaxy. We

then analyze both experimentally and theoretically the interplay between carrier lifetime, electronic coupling and extraction efficiency in the type-II SLs, and the key role of the period thickness. Finally, we compare the performance of the optimum SL-based single-junction solar cells with that of the bulk-based counterparts.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Periodicity and material quality

Figure 1a shows a sketch of the epitaxial structure and expected band structure of a GaAsSb/GaAsN SL with period thickness p (sample SL_p). Sb and N are spatially separated, giving rise to a staggered band alignment (a type-II band alignment) with electrons confined in the GaAsN layers and holes in the GaAsSb. For a [Sb] to [N] ratio of 2.8 the structure has an average lattice parameter equal to that of GaAs, fulfilling the lattice-matching condition.^[29] The SL is therefore strain balanced, with the tensile strain in the GaAsN layers counteracting the compressive strain in GaAsSb. These structures have been recently grown for the first time, and structural analyses in a 12-nm-thick period SL showed a much more accurate control of the Sb and N composition than in the bulk counterparts due to suppressed Sb-N interaction in the growth surface.^[26,27]

Figure 1. a) Sketch of the epitaxial and band structure of a SL with a period thickness p , and type-II band alignment. b) Omega-2 theta HR-XRD scans around the (004) GaAs Bragg reflection performed on the SLs with different period thickness. The period thickness t deduced from the spectra are indicated in the figure. c) Dark field 002 TEM images of the samples. The GaAsSb (bright layers) and GaAsN (dark layers) forming each period can be clearly observed in all cases. d) 15 K PL spectra from the set of SL samples with different period thickness. The inset shows the integrated intensity and FWHM of the spectra as a function of period thickness.

In the first series of samples, we compare SL structures with different nominal period thicknesses of 3, 6, 12, and 20 nm (SL_3 , SL_6 , SL_{12} , and SL_{20} , respectively). All SLs have a total thickness of

200 nm and the same Sb and N nominal contents of 3.25% and 1.20%, respectively, fulfilling the strain balance condition.^[30] Figure 1b shows high-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) θ - 2θ scans around the GaAs (004) Bragg reflection. The close match of the mean SL reflection peak with the substrate Bragg angle in all the samples indicates [strain balancing](#)^[30] an accurate composition and lattice-matching control within the whole range of periodicity. The spacing between subsequent satellite peaks allows for a precise estimation of the period thickness, found to be 3.1, 6.4, 12.6, and 19.1 nm for SL_3 , SL_6 , SL_{12} , and SL_{20} , close to the nominal design values.

Dark field 002 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of all the samples are shown in Figure 1c. In this chemically sensitive TEM imaging mode, Sb-rich regions appear brighter whereas N-rich regions appear darker than GaAs regions. A detailed analysis demonstrates that the SLs are completely pseudomorphic, with no evidence of plastic relaxation by means of dislocations or any other sort of extended defects. All samples show ~~abrupt interfaces and a~~ homogeneous composition along the whole structure (detailed TEM analyses can be found elsewhere).^[31,32] ~~Both interface roughness and alloy inhomogeneity are reduced in these structures compared to the GaAsSbN/GaAs type-I SL counterparts.~~^[27,33] The periodicity is also regular throughout the whole structure with estimated period thicknesses of 2.7, 6.7, 13.2 and 19.4 nm for SL_3 , SL_6 , SL_{12} , and SL_{20} , in good agreement with the nominal and XRD values.

-Both XRD and TEM indicate a good composition and periodicity control even for thin periods in the range of 3 nm. Moreover, [interface analysis by TEM images](#) along with the narrowness of the satellite peaks in [the XRD spectra](#) ~~point to indicate abrupt good-high~~ quality SL interfaces, ~~that which has~~ [ve](#) been shown to be critical for ~~carrier lifetime-enhanced quantum efficiency~~ [ment](#).^[34] [Indeed, interface roughness is reduced in these structures compared to the GaAsSbN/GaAs type-I SL counterparts.](#)^[27,33]

Photoluminescence (PL) measurements at 15 K were carried out for a first evaluation of the impact of the SL period on the optical properties. As shown in Figure 1d, an increasing SL period thickness results in a blueshift of the PL peak. Indeed, the effective band gap energy in $\text{GaAs}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x/\text{GaAs}_{1-y}\text{N}_y$ SLs achievable by reducing the period thickness should tend to that of a randomly alloyed bulk structure containing the same overall amount of Sb and N, i.e., $x/2$ Sb and $y/2$ N contents.^[35] The period thickness of such SL structures is therefore an additional parameter, besides the Sb and N contents, allowing for the tunability of the effective bandgap, while keeping lattice-matching condition, in order to reach the wavelengths of interest in a certain field of application. The PL blueshift with the period thickness is accompanied by a broadening of the full width at half maximum (FWHM), from 26 meV in SL_{20} to 104 meV in SL_3 , and an enhancement of the integrated intensity by a factor of ~ 1.6 from SL_{20} to SL_3 (inset of Figure 1d).

2.2. Quantum confinement, mini-band formation and radiative lifetime

Simulations of the effective bandgap through a finite differences method help to correlate the SL period thickness with the optical properties. **Figure 2a** shows the results from calculations considering the periods measured by HR-XRD θ - 2θ scans and the nominal Sb and N contents in the respective layers. The potential profile and the calculated confined states at either band are graphically shown for one GaAsSb/GaAsN period in the four SL structures. Simulations reveal an increasing evidence of miniband formation by reducing the period thickness with respect to SL_{20} , whose relatively thick period gives rise to standard quantum well-like confined states. For thinner periods, the stronger interaction among closer confined states yields stronger wavefunction overlap, ever broadened minibands and increased density of states^[36] observed in both conduction and valence bands. Therefore, the evolution of the FWHM and integrated intensity in PL spectra

as a function of period thickness is governed by the progressive formation of minibands. The reduced period thickness yields also an enlarged confinement energy of the ground state leading to a blueshift of the effective bandgap, following a similar evolution as that of the PL peak energy (Figure 2b). A bandgap tunability of ~ 80 meV is achieved within the investigated range. This confirms the presence of quantum confinement in the structures and therefore the effective bandgap tunability through period thickness.

Figure 2. a) Potential profile and calculated confined energy levels for a single period of each SL. b) Comparison between the measured PL peak energy at 15 K and the calculated ground transition energy. c) Time-resolved PL decays measured at the PL peak energy of samples SL_3 , SL_6 , SL_{12} , SL_{20} and *bulk*. The deconvoluted decay time parameters are presented in Table S1, Supporting Information. d) Weighted average radiative lifetime of the type-II SLs and calculated inverse of

the electron-hole wavefunction overlap for type-II and type-I SLs (described in Figure S1, Supporting Information) as a function of period thickness. The measured average lifetime of a 12 nm period equivalent type-I structure (SL_{I-12} , solid blue circle) and of the *bulk* sample (dotted line) are also shown.

The period thickness determines electronic coupling in the structure, which should affect radiative lifetime. Figure 2c shows TR-PL decay curves at the PL peak maxima from the set of SL structures, together with an equivalent bulk GaAsSbN reference sample grown with the same Sb and N fluxes (sample *bulk*). The change in the decay dynamics follows a clear trend whereby thinner period thickness leads to faster PL extinction, the decay behavior progressively approaching that of the bulk material. A multi-exponential fit was carried out in order to describe different regimes in the decay dynamics along the full range of time and quantitatively compare the recombination nature in the different structures. The characteristic times estimated from the different decay regimes with their relative weights, as well as the weighted average carrier lifetime, are shown in **Table S1**, Supporting Information. Significantly weaker wavefunction overlap (oscillator strengths) for period thickness starting from 12 nm yield the appearance of a long characteristic time as consequence of a more pronounced type-II-like nature.

In a first approximation, carrier radiative lifetime can be approximated by the weighted average of the characteristic times in the different decay regimes (τ). So, the estimated radiative lifetimes are represented in Figure 2d together with the inverse of the electron-hole wavefunction overlap, value directly proportional to the radiative lifetime. Such calculations as a function of the period thickness were also carried out for GaAsSbN/GaAs type-I SLs with the same Sb and N contents for comparison (see **Figure S1**, Supporting Information), and the lifetime for a 12 nm-period type-

I SL (sample SL_{I-12}) was measured experimentally (see **Table S1**, Supporting Information). As observed, there is evident good agreement between the tendencies for experimental radiative lifetimes and the theoretically estimated values for the inverse of the wavefunction overlap. A strong reduction of carrier lifetime for thinner periods is observed and predicted for the type-II SLs, which tends towards that of the bulk structure for the thinnest periods. Nevertheless, the inverse of the wavefunction overlap hardly varies with period thickness for type-I SLs, with a value close to that of the bulk. This demonstrates that in the type-II SLs we are tuning the radiative lifetime by modifying the electronic coupling in the SL. Therefore, carrier radiative lifetime can be widely tuned through the period thickness in type-II SLs, something which is not achievable in type-I SL counterparts. Despite the relatively small potential barriers due to the low N and Sb contents in these SLs, long carrier lifetimes of ~ 40 ns can be achieved for thick periods. Moreover, lifetimes characteristic of bulk and type-I SLs are achievable from a type-II SL structure with sufficiently reduced period thickness.

2.3. Extraction efficiency

A change in electronic coupling should alter also carrier transport and extraction efficiency. Indeed, quantum kinetic calculations based on the non-equilibrium Green's function formalism predict a change in the transport regime in these SLs from quasi-ballistic to sequential tunneling and thermal phonon-mediated escape when the period thickness is increased.^[37] This leads to a strong reduction of the extraction efficiency for thicknesses above 8 nm (**Figure 3**). Nevertheless, the predicted degradation of the extraction efficiency with period thickness in type-II SLs is much slower than in the standard type-I counterparts (Figure 3). Indeed, for the series of samples analyzed in previous sections (effective bandgap 1.15-1.25 eV), we would still have an extraction

efficiency of $\sim 90\%$ for 10 nm-thick periods, while it would be reduced down to 40% in equivalent type-I structures. This is due to a reduced radiative recombination in the quantum wells due to the type-II band alignment and it shows therefore how the long radiative lifetimes improve carrier extraction efficiency. The type-II SLs allow a broader range of period thicknesses to be implemented in the design of devices with a reasonable extraction efficiency. This is an additional advantage of the type-II structures.

Figure 3. Calculated carrier extraction efficiency as a function of period thickness for type-II and type-I SLs with a 1.2 eV effective bandgap (black), as well as for type-II SLs with a 1.0 eV effective bandgap (red). The calculated spectral current density under monochromatic illumination ($E=1.2$ eV) of two type-II SLs with a 1.0 eV effective bandgap and period thicknesses of 3 and 6 nm is shown below. The corresponding local density of states is shown in **Figure S2**, Supporting Information.

The onset of the extraction efficiency degradation is significantly smaller if we increase the N and Sb contents in order to get smaller effective bandgaps, since the larger confinement potentials reduce the electronic coupling. In the case of 1 eV SLs, the extraction efficiency in type-II SLs is strongly degraded for periods above 6 nm (Figure 3). Figure 3 shows also the calculated spectral current density for the 3 and 6 nm cases after above-bandgap monochromatic excitation with a photon energy of 1.2 eV (the corresponding local density of states is shown in **Figure S2**, Supporting Information). The transport mechanism is quasi-ballistic for electrons and holes in the structure with a 3 nm period. Nevertheless, a change in the transport regime for holes to thermal escape is already apparent in the 6 nm period sample. Moreover, sequential tunneling for electrons has also started in the 6 nm structure. The overall effect is a reduction in the extraction efficiency.

These results show that thick periods and, therefore, long radiative carrier lifetimes, are incompatible with a high extraction efficiency in low bandgap structures in the range of 1 eV. This means also that there is no tradeoff between absorption (enhanced for stronger electronic coupling and lower radiative lifetimes) and extraction in these SLs, since both are maximized for thin periods. Nevertheless, the period thickness cannot be arbitrarily reduced if the advantages of the spatial separation of N and Sb regarding crystal quality and composition control are to be kept, since Sb segregation would lead to a significant Sb-N interaction in the growth surface in thin period structures, as well as to Sb incorporation in the GaAsN layer.^[31]

2.4. External quantum efficiency

Taking all this into account, in order to have 1 eV layers with a high extraction efficiency periods below 6 nm must be chosen. Three p-i-n devices containing a 816 nm-thick absorbing region were fabricated to test the SLs as solar cells: two SLs with period thicknesses of 6 and 3 nm (*SC-SL₆*

and *SC-SL₃*, respectively) and a bulk layer (*SC-bulk*) as a reference. The three samples were grown under the same conditions and N and Sb fluxes, giving nominal contents of 2.4% N and 3.4% Sb. The detailed epitaxial structure of the samples and a top view of a processed device are shown in **Figure S3**, Supporting Information. The room temperature external quantum efficiency (EQE) of the three solar cells as a function of applied bias between 0 and -6 V are shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Room temperature EQE spectra as a function of reverse bias of samples *SC-bulk*, *SC-SL₆* and *SC-SL₃*. The top panels show the maximum of the EQE spectra as a function of reverse bias for the three solar cells.

The effective bandgap is in the 1 eV region, slightly shifted to higher energies in the SLs due to quantum confinement. There is a strong increase of the EQE with reverse bias in the three devices that indicates a poor carrier collection efficiency at short-circuit conditions. This results in a low EQE at 0 V. Nevertheless, the increase in EQE saturates for the SLs, meaning that complete carrier collection is achieved under reverse bias, while it monotonically increases for the bulk case in the whole range of measured voltages. Complete carrier collection is therefore not achieved in the

bulk sample in this range of voltages. The EQE under short-circuit conditions is significantly larger in the SLs than in the bulk, the larger EQE corresponding to the thinner period SL. Remarkably, this is achieved by using half the amount of N and Sb in the SLs as compared to the bulk.

The larger EQE in the *SC-SL₃* solar cell and the faster saturation with reverse bias as compared to *SC-SL₆* can be explained in terms of the larger wavefunction overlap and density of states (which enhances the absorption coefficient) and the higher extraction efficiency, as predicted by the quantum kinetics model. Nevertheless, the difference of the SL devices over the bulk must be due to different reasons, since a large density of states and 100% extraction efficiency would be expected for a perfect bulk structure. The differences could therefore be related to the material quality. In order to investigate this fact, the three samples were analyzed by TEM-related techniques that allow extracting the N and Sb distribution in the structure. The left column in **Figure 5** shows low angle annular dark field images (LAADF) in which N-containing regions appear with a brighter contrast, while the right column shows energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) maps of the Sb distribution in the very same region of the sample. In the SLs, the presence of N is well limited to the GaAsN layers, while a significant Sb segregation to the GaAsN layers is observed, as expected.^[31] Remarkably, the Sb distribution looks more inhomogeneous in the bulk than in the SLs, with a larger density of Sb-rich clusters. The alloy fluctuations can be quantified by plotting Sb content profiles in the in-plane direction, which shows a much larger standard deviation and variance in the bulk than in the SLs (see **Figure S4**, Supporting Information). The most homogeneous structure is the 6 nm period SL, in which the spatial separation of N and Sb is larger. This demonstrates that improved structural quality is obtained by avoiding the concomitant presence of N and Sb in the structure. The Sb clusters create potential wells in the valence band that could lead to hole localization in those potential minima, slowing down the hole extraction

process. Moreover, hole accumulation in the clusters could lead to Coulomb interaction effects that would also degrade transport.

Figure 5. Left column: LAADF images highlighting the N distribution (brighter contrast) of samples *SC-bulk*, *SC-SL₆* and *SC-SL₃*. N content profiles follow a step function without segregation, falling rapidly towards zero in the GaAsSb layer. Right column: EDX maps of the Sb distribution of the very same region. The in-plane Sb profiles averaged to the rectangles displayed in the figure are shown in **Figure S4**, Supporting Information.

The other important reason likely behind the improved EQE in the SLs is a reduced density of non-radiative recombination centers. It is well known that N introduces a significant amount of point defects in GaAs-based diluted nitrides, such as N interstitials,^[38,39] Ga vacancies or

interstitials associated to N,^[18,38,40,41] As antisites,^[18,41-43] etc. This is definitely one of the reasons that is hindering nitrides from their successful application in multi-junction solar cells. Moreover, in the diluted nitrides grown by plasma-assisted MBE the way to produce atomic N is to create a plasma from ultra-pure N₂. Nevertheless, several species coexist in the plasma: electrons, atomic nitrogen, diatomic nitrogen, and ionized nitrogen species.^[44,45] The ionic species in the plasma reaching the growth surface are also a source of point defects and responsible for a degradation of the optical properties of the material.^[46] Therefore, the fact that we have half the amount of N in the SLs than in the bulk, and that the exposure time to the plasma is also halved, should result in a reduced defect density in the SLs.

2.5. Single-Junction Solar Cell Performance

The reduced non-radiative recombination in the SLs should result in lower values of the dark current of the solar cell devices. **Figure 6a** shows dark IV curves of several devices in each sample in the positive voltage region. A clear reduction of the dark current is observed in both SL structures as compared to the bulk. The average values of the dark saturation current (I_0) estimated from fits to a single diode model are 5.4×10^{-10} A, 1.06×10^{-10} A and 1.18×10^{-10} A in samples *SC-bulk*, *SC-SL₃* and *SC-SL₆* respectively. I_0 is very similar in the two SL samples and ~5 times lower than in the bulk. This confirms the effectiveness of the SL approach in reducing non-radiative recombination. All the effects mentioned have a strong impact in the performance of the solar cells under working conditions. IV curves of a representative device of the three samples under AM1.5G conditions are shown in Figure 6b (5 different devices were analyzed for each structure). It must be noticed here that the poor performance is partially due to the un-optimized solar cell structures, as explained in section 4. There is a clear increase in the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) in the SLs as

compared to the reference bulk sample. This is partially due to the larger effective bandgap. Nevertheless, there is also a significant enhancement in the short circuit current density (J_{sc}) of the SL devices despite the larger effective bandgap. The average J_{sc} increases from (4.9 ± 0.5) mA/cm² in the *SC-bulk* to (6.4 ± 0.7) mA/cm² and (9.4 ± 0.2) mA/cm² in *SC-SL₆* and *SC-SL₃*, respectively. The overall effect is a strong enhancement of power conversion efficiency (PCE), as shown in the inset of Figure 6b. The average PCE is enhanced by 47% and 134% in *SC-SL₆* and *SC-SL₃* over the *SC-bulk*, respectively. As shown in previous sections, the improvements in the SLs over the bulk are mainly the result of the improved material quality (better composition homogeneity and reduced defect density), while the improvement among the SLs for thinner periods are related to a larger absorption coefficient and to a better extraction efficiency due to a change in the transport regime to quasi-ballistic.

The strong efficiency increase of 134% in single-junction solar cells is a very promising result that demonstrates that using strain-balanced GaAsSb/GaAsN type-II SLs with thin periods may be a better alternative to thick GaAsSbN layers in multi-junction solar cells.

Figure 6: a) Dark IV curves in the positive voltage region of ~ 13 different solar cells of each sample (*SC-bulk*, *SC-SL₆* and *SC-SL₃*). b) IV curves under AM1.5G conditions of a representative device of samples *SC-bulk*, *SC-SL₆* and *SC-SL₃*. The inset shows the average PCE of the three samples as a function of bandgap energy, normalized to the value of the bulk solar cell. The line shows the small expected variation of PCE due to the change in bandgap energy.

3. Conclusion

Strain-balanced GaAsSb/GaAsN SLs are shown to overcome the material quality problems inherent to the quaternary dilute nitride alloys. Besides this, they have many other advantages over bulk and type-I SL counterparts, such as a long and tunable radiative carrier lifetime that results in enhanced carrier extraction efficiency. Moreover, there is no tradeoff between carrier extraction and absorption in these structures, both being enhanced with thinner periods. All these

characteristics make short period GaAsSb/GaAsN SLs an ideal candidate to be monolithically connected in ultimately efficient (Al)InGaP/GaAs/1.0 eV/Ge multi-junction solar cells.

4. Experimental Section

Growth details: The analyzed samples were all grown by solid source molecular beam epitaxy in a Riber 32 system using GaAs (001) n^+ substrates under As_4 overpressure conditions. Each sample consists of a 250 nm-thick n-doped GaAs buffer layer, a 200 nm or 816 nm-thick active layer grown at 470 °C at a growth rate of 1 ML/s, and a 50 nm-thick p-doped GaAs layer deposited on top. The nominal n and p-type doping concentration was $2 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The Sb flux was supplied from a Knudsen effusion cell whereas the atomic N flux came from a radio-frequency plasma source using a 0.1 sccm flow of pure N_2 . A hermetic valve placed behind the plasma source provides accurate control over N flux, avoiding the presence of N background in the structure and confining it precisely on the corresponding nominal layers.^[33,47] The growth was in-situ monitored by reflective high energy electron diffraction (RHEED) which allowed the verification of a two-dimensional growth mode throughout the whole structure.

Materials characterization: TEM was used to obtain dark field 002 images, which were acquired in a JEOL 2100 microscope operating at 200 keV. LAADF imaging together with EDX spectroscopy were simultaneously performed in STEM mode in a double aberration corrected FEI Titan3 Cubed Themis operated at 200 kV. EDX mapping was carried out with four embedded Bruker SDD detectors using ChemiSTEM technology and processed with the Bruker's ESPRIT software. HR-XRD rocking-curve scans using the $Cu-K\alpha_1$ line (1.54056 Å) were performed with an X'Pert Pro Pan'alytical commercial system. Low temperature (15 K) PL measurements were carried out using a He-Ne laser. The emitted light was dispersed through a 1 m-spectrometer and

detected using a liquid-nitrogen cooled Ge-detector and standard lock-in techniques. TR-PL experiments were performed exciting the sample with 405 nm pulsed laser light. Decay curves were recorded by a time correlated single photon counting system based on a fast-infrared photomultiplier attached to a 0.3 m-focal length spectrometer. The average excitation power density was 0.6 W/cm^2 at 10 MHz. Multi-exponential deconvolution analysis was done considering the system response measured with a 980 nm ps laser. Time resolution after system response deconvolution is ~ 200 ps.

Electronic band structure calculation: Single band effective mass approximation was used with input parameters for the period thickness obtained from the HR-XRD spectra. The bandgap energy and band offsets of GaAsN were obtained considering the BAC predictions in first order perturbation theory,^[6] with the specific values for the electron effective mass and BAC parameters described elsewhere.^[48] Regarding the GaAsSb layers, their bandgap energy and band offsets were estimated using experimental results for GaAsSb pseudomorphically grown on GaAs.^[49] The hole effective mass was obtained from a linear interpolation between the binaries. The Schrödinger equation is solved with the finite differences method. The matrix element quantifying the electron-hole overlap is directly computed from the solutions of the single-band model.

Local density of states, spectral current density and extraction efficiency calculations: To model photocarrier transport under experimental conditions (finite built-in field and room temperature operation), the NEGF formalism as adapted for photovoltaic device simulation^[50] is used. The electronic structure model for the bulk constituent materials consists of a simple two band effective mass model with parameters obtained from the double BAC theory.^[51] For the realistic simulation of charge transport, the coupling of charge carriers to dispersionless polar optical phonons and the elastic interaction with acoustic phonons is considered using the Fröhlich Hamiltonian and the

deformation potential formalism, respectively. Photogeneration is described within linear coupling to the classical light field, while for the emission, the incoherent coupling to free field modes is considered.^[52] For the electron-phonon interaction, parameters for bulk GaAs were used, and a Kane energy of $(P_{cv})^2/(2m_0) = 28.8$ eV was assumed for the light-matter coupling.

Device fabrication: The thickest samples (816 nm active layer) were processed in 200 μ m-diameter mesa-etched devices using standard fabrication techniques. The mesa structures were defined by wet etching using a H_3PO_4 - H_2O_2 - H_2O (1:1:8) solution. The p-type contact, deposited on top of the mesa, was Au/Au-Zn/Au (100/800/2000 Å). A common n-type contact consisting on Au-Ge/Au (800/2000 Å) was evaporated on the substrate side. The contacts were exposed to an annealing process at 400 °C for 1 minute. It must be noticed that the solar cell structure is not optimized. Neither the thickness nor the doping level of the absorber and emitter regions were optimized, and no window layer, anti-reflection coating or back surface field layer were deposited, as the purpose of our study is at this stage mainly comparative.

Device characterization: Photocurrent measurements were carried out using light from a QTH lamp, which was dispersed through a 0.34 m monochromator and directed through the optical path to the sample. A K230 Keithley sourcemeter as well as a K617 Keithley electrometer were employed. To obtain the EQE, the photocurrent data was first converted into responsivity dividing by the power per unit area of the QTH lamp (measured using a calibrated Si photodiode and a pyroelectric photodetector) multiplied by the diode top metal-free area. Finally, responsivity was converted to EQE multiplying by the photon energy divided by the electron charge. Current-voltage curves under AM1.5G conditions were measured using an Oriel solar simulator with sample temperature control at 25°C.

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